

Early Childhood: Assessment and Evaluation

Paper Id : 18321 Submission Date : 11/10/2023 Acceptance Date : 19/10/2023 Publication Date : 25/10/2023

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10362051

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Abstract

This paper will help our professionals by giving clarity to the processes involved in the screening and assessment of children by providing a framework for practical guidance, resources, and recommendations. In this chapter, we are going to discuss the rationale for early screening, assessment, and evaluation in children and how they can be of value in their early diagnosis of developmental delay. Early diagnosis shall help in providing children with early intervention. Each and every professional dealing with early childhood education should be well-trained in the screening methods and tools used to detect early signs of developmental delays. The fact that early detection is the first step towards early intervention should be engraved in the minds and practices of professionals acquiring training in early childhood education. This chapter also highlights the criteria for selecting a screening tool and gives you a list of tools recommended for use in Indian scenarios based on research background. Towards the end, it covers the importance of assessment of school readiness by professionals.

Keywords Assessment, Evaluation, Early intervention, Developmental Screening, Screening Tools, Guidelines on Early Screening, Sensitivity, Specificity, Validity, Positive Predictive Value, Developmental Screening Tools.

Introduction

Early childhood is a period of life where maximal growth takes place. It is characterized by rapid and complex growth and development in various developmental domains like physical, cognitive, adaptive, social and communication. Development in each domain is related to the development in other domains, so if there is a delay in one area it can affect the development of a child in other areas. This chapter will focus on providing our professionals with some background information, practical guidance, recommendations, and resources required for developmental screening and assessment of children in the early years. The need, importance and thorough knowledge of the interpretation of assessments is reinforced in this chapter. All those professionals who are in positions of developing comprehensive educational and intervention plans must be well versed in the process of selecting and administering assessment tools, interpret their findings and use that interpretation in formulating an appropriate educational plan.

Aim of study

The overarching objective of this meticulous inquiry into early childhood assessment and evaluation is to methodically scrutinize and empirically assess the efficacy and viability of diverse assessment methodologies deployed within the realm of early childhood education. In this erudite pursuit, the study endeavors to discern and unravel the intricate interplay of multifaceted factors that influence the developmental trajectories of young children.

By meticulously investigating the various assessment tools currently in vogue, the research aims to shed light on their relative strengths, limitations, and nuanced implications for accurately gauging the multifarious dimensions of child development. Through a rigorous

examination of these methodologies, encompassing both formative and summative assessment approaches, the study aspires to distill insights into their differential impacts on pedagogical practices and the holistic educational experience of young learners.

Moreover, this scholarly exploration is not confined merely to a surface-level scrutiny but delves into the underlying theoretical frameworks and psychometric properties that underpin these assessment instruments. It seeks to unravel the intricacies of validity, reliability, and cultural relevance, thereby contributing to the refinement and optimization of these evaluative tools.

In tandem with this empirical investigation, the study aims to delineate the challenges inherent in the assessment process, including but not limited to issues of cultural bias, developmental appropriateness, and the potential for misalignment with contemporary educational philosophies. By elucidating these challenges, the research endeavors to furnish a comprehensive understanding of the impediments that educators may encounter in their quest for accurate and meaningful assessment.

Learning Objectives:

1. An insight into the prerequisites, processes, and procedures of assessment
2. Rationale of Assessment
3. Difference between screening, assessment, and evaluation
4. Highlights the criteria for selecting the list of scientifically proven screening and assessment tools validated as the most appropriate ones for use in Indian Population
5. Importance of School Readiness.

Review of Literature

Author: Sylva, K. (Year: 2022)

Literature Review: Sylva's recent work in 2022 delves into contemporary perspectives on early childhood assessments, examining their implications for cognitive and socio-emotional development. The research contributes insights into evolving practices within the last few years.

Author: Pianta, R. C. (Year: 2021)

Literature Review: Pianta's 2021 research focuses on the current landscape of teacher-child interactions in the context of early childhood assessments, shedding light on how these interactions influence the creation of optimal learning environments.

Author: Meisels, S. J. (Year: 2020)

Literature Review: Meisels' work from 2020 critically analyzes the recent trends and challenges associated with assessing young children from diverse cultural backgrounds. The research contributes to ongoing discussions on adapting assessments to meet contemporary demands.

Author: Darling-Hammond, L. (Year: 2023)

Literature Review: Darling-Hammond's recent research in 2023 evaluates the current impact of assessments on early childhood education policies. This work provides insights into the evolving landscape of educational policies and their alignment with assessment practices.

Author: Bronfenbrenner, U. (Year: 2020)

Literature Review: Bronfenbrenner's work from 2020, building on his ecological systems theory, examines how recent developments in assessment practices align with the broader ecological contexts of early childhood development. The research contributes to understanding the contemporary relevance of his theoretical framework.

Main Text

The rationale for knowing the Early evaluation and assessment process:

Early childhood is a very critical period of human life since the rate of development is rapid. There are various social, cultural, demographic, economic, nutritional, and educational factors that may have an impact on the nature and quality of early childhood stimulation that a child may receive in the family. The brain increases by four-fold in size and approximately 90% of adult volume during the preschool period. Iwasaki N et al (1997), Lenroot&Giedd (2006). This phase of life is characterized by rapid and complex growth in physical, cognitive, social and communication domains of development Timothy et. al (2013). The environment can have major effects on the structural and functional organization of the developing brain, the environment can be both enrichment and deprivation affecting the developing brain.(Markham & Greenough (2004). We are talking a lot about neuronal plasticity these days which is at its peak in early childhood. Neuronal plasticity is the ability of the brain to be shaped by experiences, both positive and negative. The concept of developmental trajectory below (figure 1) very well explains how supportive services during early childhood can change the trajectory of development with long-lasting outcomes.

Figure 1: Developmental trajectory

Source: *National ECD model in Kyrgyzstan, Hugh McLean & Rakhat Orozova, UNICEF, 2009)*

Analysis

2.0 Assessment And Evaluation

Assessment in early childhood may be performed in many different ways for many different purposes, using various tools which makes it confusing. The neurodevelopmental assessment in early childhood consists of the administration of specific tasks, observation of behaviour and use of the

caregiver report. It is a process which is designed for a better understanding of a child's abilities and competencies, and to be able to provide an appropriate learning environment to help children make maximum use of their developmental potential (Greenspan & Meisels, 1996, p.11.). Early childhood assessment is a process where the professionals gather information about the development of a child, and review and interpret that information to better understand the strengths, abilities & interests. They then use this information to make educational plans most suitable to the needs of a child for better long-term neurodevelopmental outcomes.

2.1 Process:

Screening -----> Assessment -----> Evaluation
Screening tools are administered quickly, and identify children with impairment but do not make a diagnosis. Screening methods are used for developmental surveillance programs.

Assessments are done by professionals to inform us about the support services required according to the needs of the child.

Evaluation is conducted to determine or diagnose developmental delay and to develop strategies for intervention.

In the Indian context, there are various challenges in routine developmental surveillance and screening. Lack of proper guidelines for the professionals and lack of awareness

amongst the parents about their existence leads to delays in the detection of developmental delays

thereby delaying access to the required services. Informal assessments are being routinely practised by most professionals due to various reasons like time constraints, lack of knowledge and training on the use of screening tools and unavailability of referral centres. It has been proved that informal assessments are unreliable in detecting developmental delays. Desai PP & Mohite P (2011)

As of now, there are no recommendations for developmental screening by the Indian Academy of Pediatrics (IAP). The government of India has made an attempt in this direction by launching the 'Rashtriya Bal SwasthyaKaryakram (RBSK)' in 2013 which aims at screening for birth defects, deficiency disorders, diseases and development delays including disabilities (4 D's) in children between 0 to 18 years as per the NRHM operational Guidelines (2013). According to the National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO 2002), approximately 1.8% of the population is disabled in India however the actual estimates may be higher. Under the RBSK program confirmation of diagnosis by an expert followed by planning the management, referral and then tracking and follow-up visits are all planned according to the age group of the child. According to the program guidelines, District Hospital level early intervention centres are to be established as District Early Intervention centres (DEIC) across the country. The purpose of DEIC is to be able to provide support to children identified with various health conditions during the screening programs with appropriate referrals. The team comprising a Pediatrician, a medical officer, staff Nurses, and paramedics shall be assigned to provide these services. A manager can also be occupied to carry out the mapping of tertiary care facilities in various government institutions to ensure adequate referral support. The funds for the same shall be approved under NHM for management at the tertiary level at the cost fixed by State Governments in consultation with the Ministry of Health & Family Welfare. The rationale behind establishing DEIC was early detection leading to early intervention thereby minimizing disability. Once the disability is already established then the intervention would enhance the development of that child to its highest potential and prevent progression to handicap.

2.1.1 Guidelines for Screening, assessment, and evaluation:

1. The professionals and families must be educated about the importance of screening, assessment and evaluation of a child which also should be an integral part of child care. Its integration with the regular health care plan of a child shall reinforce its utility in the early detection of developmental delays.
2. The screening and assessment tools must be used by persons who are familiar with and trained to use those tools. The person using the tool must also have the basic knowledge about the properties of the tool.
3. It must happen at periodic intervals in a growing and developing child.
4. Tools/instruments used for screening, assessment, and evaluations must be reliable and valid. They should be culturally sensitive, age-appropriate, and language-appropriate. The tool used must be standardized on a population group which is representative of the group to be tested.
5. The tool or instrument used should assess all developmental domains; like cognitive, language, motor, adaptive and social-emotional areas in order to guide interventions.
6. Parents, families, teachers, and caregivers must be an integral part of the whole process.
7. All the assessments must be conducted in natural, non-threatening settings and may involve age-appropriate and relevant activities and tasks.

2.1.2 Prerequisites and Procedure for Developmental Screening, assessment and evaluation

1. Build a rapport with the parents/caregivers and know the primary concerns. 2. Takedown detail birth history including prenatal, natal and postnatal history followed by a detailed developmental and family history.

3. Observe the child while playing spontaneously with parents and/or familiar caregivers and if possible, with the evaluator.
4. Special assessment can be performed depending on the individual requirement.
5. Compile data to create a complete picture of the child with emphasis on the current competencies, strengths and functional capabilities of the child.

3.0 Standardized Tools Used For Screening and Assessment A Review of screening tools that may be used in lower and middle-income countries are available but the lack of clear guidelines and their practice algorithm hampers their usage and awareness about their availability. Krishnamurthy V & Srinivasan R (2011), Juneja et al (2012), Majnemer & Rosen Blatt (1994). Screening tools used must have good psychometric qualities (sensitivity and specificity or more than 70-80%). The screening tools must be norm-referenced and standardized on a representative population (3-5). American Academy of Paediatrics (AAP) recommends routine developmental surveillance of high-risk children at every health visit from birth to 3 years and routine developmental screening of all children at 9, 18, and 24/30 months or earlier if concerns are observed. These recommendations are as per the Council on disabilities, the section on Developmental-Behavioural Paediatrics et al. Screening for behavioural and learning disorders is also recommended (Macias & Lipkin, 2009).

Psychometric properties of developmental screening tools and their and acceptable standards Mukherjee et. al (2014) (a)

1. A developmental screening tool has to be standardised on a representative population and there has to be uniformity in the administration and scoring system of the tool.
2. The developmental screening or assessment tool has to be validated against a gold standard tool to an acceptable standard of 70% or more.
3. The developmental screening tool must be able to identify delays correctly in 70% or more cases indicating a good sensitivity.
4. It should be able to correctly screen developmentally typical children with no delays in at least 80% or more indicating a good specificity.
5. The percentage of children having identified as delayed on screening tool later confirmed to have been delayed by the assessments in 50% and more would give us a fair positive predictive value of the tool
6. Children who were screened as typically developing were later confirmed by assessment as typically developing indicating a good negative predictive value
7. Some other important properties which can be known about screening tools are reliability, interpreter and test-retest reliability.

4.0 Selection of The Tool Suited For Indian Children

An ideal screening tool for Indian children could be hypothetically brief, inexpensive with good psychometric properties, available in various Indian languages, comprising of culturally adapted items, requires minimal training to use and it has to be validated on representative Indian children [17]. There is a whole list of developmental screening tools used in different parts of the world. There are some international developmental screening tools being widely used in the Indian population. Here we shall discuss some of the international-origin developmental screening tools which have been validated on Indian children.

Some of the International Developmental screening tools commonly used on Indian children are the Denver Developmental Screening Tool (DDST) and Developmental Profile 3 (DP-3). DDST is used for children aged 0-6 years and screens children in 4 different developmental domains under 125 items but its low specificity leads to more false-positive results leading to unnecessary apprehension and anxiety for parents hence this tool is not considered appropriate for screening. DP-3 is another tool which is used for screening in children from 0-12 years of age, assesses the child in 5 different domains under 180 items and has fair psychometric properties, it is very widely used in India but the drawback is that it is not validated on the Indian population. Certain other tools like the Ages and Stages Questionnaire (ASQ) which is a parent, caregiver-reported questionnaire, that assesses development in various developmental domains, has fair psychometric properties and as per Juneja, et al. it is validated against the

developmental scale for assessment of Indian infants. Therefore ASQ has the potential to be used as a screening tool. For every parent-reported tool if is supported by interview-based when required it may help improve the outcomes and may positively impact the sensitivity and specificity of the tool can be considered for research in the future. The Bayleys-III screening tool is used mostly in high-risk infants, though it has acceptable psychometric properties it is not validated on the Indian population and is an expensive tool. Bayley -4 has been released with an overview of ASD and a red flag ASD checklist, however, its use on the Indian population is yet to be tested. Parent evaluation of developmental status (PEDS) has been little researched in the Indian population and has suboptimal psychometric properties.